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Path to Hollywood

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Post-Bop Trauma: Polish Crime-Jazz Cinema and Its Westward Path to Hollywood

DAVID MELBYE

Abstract. The global spread of American popular music alongside the pervasive distribution of 1940s and '50s crime dramas, among other Hollywood products, encouraged a prejudicial association between jazz and social deviance in the form of sexual indulgence, criminality, ethnic otherness, or configurations of each reflecting the others. At the same time, African American and other visionaries were pushing the jazz idiom in bold new directions according to their own creative ambitions. Nevertheless, these experimental jazz values were increasingly appropriated in jazz-inflected film scores to reinforce traumatic narrative contexts across the 1960s—as visceral iterations of horror jazz. The Polish crime-jazz association is unique within this transnational artistic context for mobilizing a palpable countercurrent of feature filmmaking, particularly through the work of filmmaker Roman Polanski and his favored composer Krzysztof Komeda, whose intersecting international career paths would eventually meet in Hollywood. Prominent African American jazz musicians, bandleader-drummer Chico Hamilton among them, also contributed to this westward momentum. Ironically, the cinematic trend toward disturbing psychological evocations of otherness represented a professional opportunity for modern jazz innovators unavailable to them otherwise at this time.

Keywords: jazz, crime drama, Roman Polanski, Krzysztof Komeda

At the start of the influential Hollywood horror film *Rosemary's Baby* (Roman Polanski, 1968), credits roll out over an aerial scan of New York City centering on the evocatively neogothic Dakota apartment building. A delicate female vocal melody anticipates the tale of a young woman's vulnerability to Satanic conspirators in residence there. In its minor key and $\frac{3}{4}$ time, the supportive orchestral music would seem broadly appropriate in a dramatic context, save for the repeated dissonant intervals on harpsichord, alternating with kalimba, hinting that something perverse threatens to undermine the so-titled "Lullaby" experience of new motherhood. Because this film

is decidedly an appeal to the increasingly visceral horror genre and its resonance with mainstream audiences in the postwar era, such a harmonic strategy, regardless of instrumentation, would seem well within the conventions of feature film scoring. Later in the film, however, this symphonic horror score conjures semblances of the modern jazz idiom—at one point with an audible rhythm section walking a relentless six-note pattern to serve a dissonant squealing trumpet not so dissimilar from the exploratory soloing found on albums of John Coltrane, Ornette Coleman, Sun Ra, and so many other African American jazz pioneers around this time.

But because these artists were more interested in musical transcendence than evoking horror per se, any correlation between post-bop jazz and onscreen depictions of fear and psychological trauma cannot be considered inherent. Rather, their implied relationship in this context involves a complex confluence of cultural trajectories, which, in the case of *Rosemary's Baby*, should be traced through the running collaboration between Polish writer-director Roman Polanski and jazz composer Krzysztof Komeda, here credited safely for American audiences as “Christopher” Komeda. Polish new wave cinema of the 1960s played a palpable role in encouraging the deployment of jazz values for psychological emphasis in auteur-driven New Hollywood crime films of the 1970s such as Francis Ford Coppola’s *The Conversation* (1974) and Martin Scorsese’s *Taxi Driver* (1976). Beyond any exhibition of these foreign films in American art-house theaters, influence from abroad is attributable to the migrating presence of Polanski as well as Polish writer-director Jerzy Skolimowski—and their integration of Komeda’s jazz-inflected film scores. This is not to imply, of course, that *Rosemary's Baby* should be understood instead as a Polish film per se but rather that diasporas of jazz activity in narrative cinema emanating from Hollywood would eventually return to American popular consciousness as horror jazz.

Prominent African American jazz musicians were also invited to compose soundtracks for Hollywood films at this time, although such a career path would commence with at least one overseas production before that musician would be allowed an assignment. Prior to scoring the socially consciousness noir film *Odds Against Tomorrow* (Robert Wise, 1959) in the US, John Lewis composed the music with the Modern Jazz Quartet for the French film *No Sun in Venice* (Roger Vadim, 1957) and prior to Miles Davis’s improvisational jazz

score for Louis Malle’s *Elevator to the Gallops* (1958). Quincy Jones scored the Swedish juvenile delinquency film *The Boy in the Tree* (Arne Sucksdorff, 1961) before beginning his extended run in Hollywood with the jazz-trauma films *The Pawnbroker* (Sidney Lumet, 1964) and *In Cold Blood* (Richard Brooks, 1967). Herbie Hancock scored Michelangelo Antonioni’s modernist British film *Blow-Up* (1966) also before commencing his long tenure as a composer in Hollywood. Like bebop saxophonist Dexter Gordon, African American jazz musicians found they were greeted more enthusiastically overseas, and so many of them expatriated for this among other opportunities unavailable to them at home.

I suggest the impulse toward disturbing psychological appropriations of the modern jazz idiom onscreen was a collaborative effort between European filmmakers and an extended cohort of jazz composers that did not exclude African American musicians. The Polish case demonstrates this trend, also making it a fruitful nexus through which to recognize these trajectories of influence at work. When Komeda was unable to obtain a work visa, Chico Hamilton replaced him to score Polanski’s British psychological horror entry *Repulsion* (1965), before making soundtracks for Hollywood crime films in the 1970s. Komeda also worked with Don Cherry and other African American jazz musicians—and these collective efforts influenced Hollywood production in turn.

Jazz in Poland

Appreciated as new and exciting dance music, as was the case in the US, jazz rapidly permeated mainstream Polish society in the 1920s and ’30s despite resistance from conservative factions. Although professionally not addressing considerations of racial identity within this cultural climate, Igor Pietraszewski’s 2014 study *Jazz in Poland: Improvised Freedom* nevertheless cites an

example of racist attitudes toward jazz values in a 1922 periodical. At a local nightclub, it reported, “some were outraged by the jazz band playing a foxtrot consisting of adaptations of Chopin’s *Fantasy Impromptu* cis-mol (op. 66), waltz *Des-dur* (op. 64, no. 1), and *Funeral March!* What a sight it was: those mooring trumpets, howling whistles, whirring of various drums, castanets, xylophones, and other necessary attributes of that negro music.”¹ Beyond any notion that the infiltration of a foreign idiom could contaminate music deemed vital to Polish heritage, also implied here is a perceived dichotomy between a civilized and/or refined degree of musical expression and that of a wild and/or primitive quality attributed to the African ethnicity of its creators.

While these fears of cultural contamination certainly were not particular to Poland, younger generations in both America and Europe appreciated jazz for its adaptability to other musical idioms. Outside of its protestations, this article’s appearance attests to the notion that jazz in Poland embraced musical values deemed essential to the idiom’s unique appeal, namely its rhythmic emphasis and spontaneous expression, while at the same time applying these values to classical melodies and folk songs. Pietraszewski also affirms that the influx of Hollywood films at this time, including *The Jazz Singer* and many others, brought the awareness of jazz music and the infectiousness of swing to mass audiences.² By the end of the 1920s, he asserts, jazz in Poland had transcended its function as dance music and was being positioned as serious music to be enjoyed in concert halls alongside symphony orchestras. Although the music was repressed during the period of the German occupation, it reemerged in the postwar years as a democratized artform not only available to elites at clubs and theaters. Jazz, according to Pietraszewski, even took on connotations of resistance based on its association with American allies.³ From 1946 to 1958, when

Stalinist control was in effect, this institutionalization of jazz music was again put in check. Beyond being perceived by the Soviet regime as a manifestation of capitalist expressivity, the mostly instrumental iterations of jazz were hardly in any position to propagate ideals of socialism. Pietraszewski maintains:

It was then that the so-called “founding myth emerged,” whose main idea was the lack of acceptance of the new situation. It was not an active resistance, but rather an opposition to the imposed top-down ideological and doctrinal content of socialist realist model of cultural policy. The jazzman, without a clearly defined role within the system, was a nonconformist and an outsider excluded from social, political, and institutional life. As a result, the image (only partly true) of oppressed jazz musicians emerged, which seemed more open to the non-socialist world and society. The founding myth shaped a kind of stereotyped model of the jazzman as an anti-systemic rebel, free from the institutional system and its restrictions. The jazz community contested bureaucracy and dullness of cultural institutions, as well as the socialist realist idea of art controlled by the state through the accepted system of privileges and restrictions. The jazzman was condemned to existence beyond the institutional network of social roles imposed by the system.⁴

In this way, the embrace of the modern jazz idiom in postwar Poland, often finding its way to Polish listeners via American military radio stations, was a form of co-optation akin to that of the Beat movement in America. Magdalena Grzebałkowska’s biography of jazz composer Krzysztof Trzcinski (Komeda), quoting a Polish columnist of the time, describes this mythologization process as follows:

“Jazz. Wild, Negro sounds. A crazy tune without a tune, which even a madman couldn’t pick up. . . . For pity’s sake, you

radio people, have mercy on us.” On the Polish radio sets you can hear Europe. You turn the dial, slowly, and then, suddenly, there’s jazz on the American Forces Network (AFN), broadcasting out of Paris for the American military stationed in Europe and North Africa. Of all the Trzcinski family, it’s Krzysztof that likes listening to the radio the most.⁵

Later, she quotes Komeda reflecting on the early development of his own music:

It somehow seemed to me these few phrases, evocative of Negro spirituals, of the extremely jazzy kind of melancholy of the Blacks, would make a better jazzy “signature tune” than some hackneyed riff. And that’s how the Polish jazz signature tune was born: the fruit of my own ignorance, as Foster (the tune’s composer) was white and used to write music for the so-called “minstrel shows,” where white actors used to apply black make-up and pretend to be Black people cavorting about happily on plantations in Alabama.⁶

Here, Komeda romanticizes the African American experience of enslavement as responsible for a characteristic “melancholy” opposite to the “triumph of the Negro spirit” articulated in Edward O. Bland’s *The Cry of*

Jazz (1959), a pseudo-documentary contrasting popular white perceptions of jazz vs. the African American experience implied within its form. This is similar to Jon Panish’s account of the Beat movement’s identification with the Black jazz soloist as the key ingredient of what defined the emerging bebop sound rather than any African American solidarity reflected by their ensembles’ collective efforts to transcend swing as the music of choice for white America.⁷ In any case, even if Komeda could be referring to the blues inflection of the jazz idiom’s emphasis on the pentatonic scale, Stephen Foster’s major-key melodies, while evoking a doleful touch of folk nostalgia, are scarcely “melancholic.” What may be more significant in the Polish composer’s misperception here is his inclination to convey traumatic psychological experience through the jazz idiom. Beyond any embrace of jazz music as a sociological form of resistance to repressive cultural conditions, Komeda and other Polish jazz musicians recognized a potential for modern jazz values to inflect the composition of film scores toward a more subjectivized approach to audiovisual narrative.

In the case of Poland, unlike other overseas national contexts, the cultural trajectory

Figure 1. *The Cry of Jazz* (1959). Presented as a casual debate between an integrated assemblage of young men and women having just attended a local performance, the position is put forth that, rather than a shared American artform, “jazz is the musical expression of the triumph of the Negro spirit.” Invocations of the modern jazz idiom in global crime dramas of the ensuing decade do not echo this sensibility.

of the crime-jazz association did not emulate 1950s Hollywood in terms of the urban nightclub scenarios analyzed in David Butler's *Jazz Noir* or Jans B. Wager's *Jazz and Cocktails* wherein principal characters and other patrons gather to enjoy alcoholic beverages and take in the greater ambience provided by jazz performers.⁸ Instead, it is safer to say the affiliation of jazz with criminality commenced with an already perceived potential for the modern jazz idiom to score both diegetic action *and* atmosphere. This was based on the example set by French New Wave films, director Louis Malle's crime drama *Elevator to the Gallows*, with its improvisational jazz cues, among them. In the wake of Stalin's death in 1953, the less restrictive conditions of the so-called Soviet Thaw encouraged Polish filmmaking to pursue new paths.

Events in 1956 that included Khrushchev's speech condemning Stalinist brutality, Polish President Bolesław Bierut's subsequent death in Moscow, and the October uprisings against the Soviet regime in central Europe prompted the revitalization of Polish cinema culture. According to Marek Haltof's study on the topic, "The disappointment with the Stalinist period, the urge to represent reality's complex nature, and the desire to confront issues that had functioned as taboos in the Polish political as well as cultural life created a stimulating atmosphere for young filmmakers."⁹ Based on the diverse intentions and approaches of these filmmakers in the latter half of the 1950s, Haltof finds the historical notion of a "Polish School" problematic. Nevertheless, he cites Polish historian Stanisław Ozimek's account of a psychological-existential trend in the films of Wojciech J. Has, Stanisław Lenartowicz, and Jerzy Kawalerowicz.¹⁰ Within this artistic climate of emerging visionaries interested in contemporary issues, the modern jazz idiom presented a wellspring of aesthetic opportunity.

Night Train (1959)

Kawalerowicz's film *Night Train* (1959), whose jazz score was composed by Andrzej Trzaskowski, is a productive place to begin a consideration of jazz's presence in Polish crime-oriented cinema. This acclaimed film focuses on the developing rapport of a man (Leon Niemczyk) and a woman (Lucyna Winnicka) reluctantly occupying the same compartment of a train. When policemen come aboard in search of a murder suspect, the male passenger, Jerzy, is taken into custody. But after the female passenger, Marta, reveals she obtained her ticket from a different man hiding in the next car, the authorities realize their criminal is still at large. Yanking the emergency cord to stop the train before he is located, the actual culprit (Roland Głowacki) flees into the countryside but is just as soon apprehended by a horde of male passengers. The journey resumes, and the train finally reaches its destination on the Baltic coast without further incident. Rather than depicting any murder or other violent crime, the narrative pursues a mostly psychological dimension through its portrayal of normal law-abiding passengers and their interactions.

Before the presence of jazz can be considered here, it is vital to understand how a film where no major transgression is portrayed still functions as crime-oriented. Pointing to the film's "Hitchcockian overtones," Haltof affirms that "the film becomes a murder mystery when an afternoon newspaper reports the case of a wife murdered by her husband; Jerzy's nervousness makes him a possible suspect."¹¹ I would suggest, moreover, that this film is invested in demonstrating an all-too-human tendency to project personal traumas onto others instead of confronting them directly. Early on, another female passenger (Teresa Szmigiéłówna) reveals her attraction to Jerzy by bumping into him as he boards the train. Beyond the married

woman's persistent attempts to impress herself upon him, this initial moment launches the film's fixation on nuances of heterosexual relations. If this contained environment may be said to function as a microcosm for postwar society in Poland, it is a community oriented around sexual coupling. As a result, the initial mention of a violent crime seems more like casual banter between passengers than any mobilization of predominant mystery or suspense. Based on Haltof's reference to Hitchcock's films, one may be tempted to compare this sexualized train trip to that in *North by Northwest*, also released in 1959, during which the male protagonist (Cary Grant) is seduced by a woman (Eva Marie Saint) who turns out to be complicit in the larger diabolical scheme against him. In any case, the two male passengers' discussion of murder in *Night Train* seems, at first, merely ancillary to the ever-present array of sexual tensions at hand.

As the film progresses, however, what appeared to have been only casual mention of daily events becomes a central concern for this impromptu community of Polish civilians. At one point, one of the said male passengers addresses a priest about the possibility for criminal exoneration through holy confession. In this way, criminality, as an existential concern, just barely functions as a lynchpin for the first half of the film, that is, until the killer mentioned in the newspaper is revealed to be on board. Once the stow-away is identified and caught, the narrative resumes its emphasis on flirtation between men and women. As it turns out, criminality and sexual desire are intertwined in this film in a way that understandably bears vague comparison to Hitchcock's work. When pursuers eventually surround the fugitive in a rural cemetery, one of them begins kicking him on the ground and, in the process, melts down in tears. It is hereby implied that this passenger has positioned the criminal as a scapegoat for something deeply personal and

unrelated to the crime itself. This scene of excessive vigilantism among so many crucifixes projecting from the ground reconfigures the reprehensible wife killer as sympathetic. He is possibly even a martyr figure for social forces beyond his and everyone else's control. Inevitably, one is compelled to correlate this singular event with Marta's ultimate realization that the man she intended to meet at the end of the journey was only using her as a "mirror" for his own obsessions. The character decides that "nobody wants to love. Everybody wants to be loved." Disembarking from the train, she wanders off alone toward a dreary windswept coastline.

The presence of jazz reinforces *Night Train's* attempt to reflect a society plagued by the modern condition of self-absorption as well as displaced, potentially violent trauma. Using mostly a theme-and-variations approach, Trzaskowski's combo jazz provides a generally sultry, if not somber, mood via the minor blues melody of Artie Shaw's "Moon Ray." Made more atmospheric by swapping the upbeat swing rhythm and lovelorn lyrics with a wordless female vocal line, this theme is introduced in the opening overhead shot of the film. In a modernist framing akin to another urban rat-race shot in Skolimowski's experimental Polish film *Barrier* (1966), people on the station platform walk back and forth past each other perpetually as a human mass. Initially, then, the soundtrack evokes the hopeless drudgery of the human condition. Subsequently, however, the same music reappears when a tighter shot of passengers boarding the train centers on a young woman carrying a portable radio. Thus, the film indicates that the jazz we hear is also the popular music enjoyed by common folk in this context. The music persists as the camera follows the woman along the corridor and then dies out as she closes her compartment door.

Instead of pursuing symphonic conventions of soundtrack music, *Night Train*

Figure 2. *Night Train* (1959). Trzaskowski's combo jazz rendition of Artie Shaw's "Moon Ray" provides somber reinforcement to an overhead framing of urban sprawl on the train platform. Later, the same music scores the malaise of individual passengers staring out the window during the journey.

alternates between diegetic and extradiegetic jazz. Later, when Marta stares out the window of the compartment, the female vocal line returns as soundtrack and so assumes a more psychological dimension. Such is a recurrent strategy in the film applied when other characters also find themselves looking out the window in private reflection. Based on influence of the Modern Jazz Quartet, a vibraphone interpretation of the Shaw melody replaces the vocal line in the first moment where Marta and Jerzy reluctantly find themselves alone together in such a cramped space. In this context, the jazz underscores the sexual tension between them and persists in this function as the male character exits the compartment into the corridor—only to encounter the unwanted advances of the married woman. Upbeat combo jazz can be heard subsequently inside a station bar where, amid a train stop, this character continues her fruitless designs upon the male protagonist. In this shot, the jazz ensemble and couples dancing are barely discernable in the blurred background of the frame, but it is otherwise implied that this live music is a familiar trapping of Polish urbanity. Taken together, these various diegetic and extradiegetic

deployments of jazz constitute a jazz world to be found in other crime-oriented films of this period. This approach is akin to what happens, for example, in Douglas Sirk's melodrama *Imitation of Life* (1959). Although this Hollywood production functions less as a crime drama, a particular scene features pleasant combo jazz coming from inside a nearby nightclub that accelerates abruptly into a louder Afro-Cuban rhythm as the young female character of mixed ethnicity (Susan Kohner) is beaten by her suspicious white boyfriend (Troy Donahue) in an alleyway. Although jazz never reinforces any intense action or violent imagery in the Polish film, not even the fugitive's thwarted escape, it participates in the film's larger configuration of a world gone wrong according to the postwar psyche. Social deviance, in the form of the wife killer, is merely an extreme degree of a tendency to be found among the other passengers. The momentum of jazz in this film, as both an externalized vestige of popular culture and an internalized aspect of private trauma, accumulates primarily through a series of train compartment scenes with the male and female protagonists. After lashing out at Marta for resembling a corpse under a sheet, Jerzy finally admits

his medical skills were insufficient to save a young woman after her attempted suicide earlier that day. Taking out her own frustrations on Jerzy, Marta makes her own confession about the man she intended to meet. In this context, with her self-absorbed husband in the adjacent compartment, the hovering married woman's loneliness is also misdirected at an indifferent stranger. While these characters' aversion toward criminality is not correlated with any perception of ethnic otherness per se, the film paves the way nevertheless for a continued association between jazz and inner angst in Polish cinema that would eventually push westward.

***Two Men and a Wardrobe* (1958)**

Trzaskowski and Komeda were both major figures in the rise of modern, improvisational combo jazz in Poland, and both also composed jazz scores for films across the 1960s. Unlike Trzaskowski, however, Komeda would take his career far beyond Polish borders, eventually making his way to Hollywood. There, his life would be cut short by a tragic accident. The jazz-inflected film scores that Komeda was able to accomplish reflect a patterned association with social deviance. Moreover, these scores demonstrate his investment in the idiom's potential to reinforce psychological trauma, even if these deployments of jazz values compromised improvisation. Much of this westward momentum was facilitated through filmmakers Roman Polanski and Jerzy Skolimowski, both expatriating from Poland when creative opportunity there, once again, became limited. Before *Night Train* would appear, Polanski approached Komeda to score his mostly silent student film *Two Men and a Wardrobe* (1958). The filmmaker claimed, "I had my eye on someone who'd be able to come up with a suitable musical setting for *Two Men and a Wardrobe*—something with a cool style, something quirky enough to emphasize the

absurdity of the situation in which my protagonists find themselves."¹² Both films position criminal violence as a reflection of a dysfunctional society. The feature film, however, is far less interested in portraying any act of crime, whereas Polanski's short embraces violence as a visceral spectacle anticipating his eventual penchant for horror.

Polanski's allegorical approach has two men (Jakub Goldberg and Henryk Kluba) emerging from the sea and carrying a large wardrobe. Peripheral to any urban zone at first, they progress into a typical cityscape of paved roads with tall buildings, hotels, restaurants, alleyways, and junkyards. Somewhat open-ended as a metaphor, the cumbersome piece of furniture at least establishes their inability to integrate into the community. Everywhere they attempt to haul the obtrusive object they are understandably turned away. *Two Men and a Wardrobe's* unsympathetic progression is, moreover, a means, nevertheless, to expose the socially deviant conditions these men encounter firsthand—or merely pass through on their uncertain course. In multiple cases of deliberate framing, the camera de-emphasizes the pair and their wardrobe so that the film can focus on criminal behaviors instead. Early on, for example, as the two men cross the frame in the background, the foreground features two youths looking toward them from a bridge, and one of them lifts the wallet out of the other's back pocket. Later in the film, the camera pans away from the pair and follows a drunk stumbling up a staircase, and it allows them to subsequently leave the frame so it can witness an individual bashing another on the head with a rock. This latter moment anticipates Polanski's fixation on graphic violence well beyond his continued collaborations with Komeda. With scarcely anything accomplished, the film's two characters return to the ocean from where they first emerged, and yet their brief visitation suffices as a means to reveal the city's hostile landscape.

Komeda's film-scoring palette, variously combining piano, clarinet, saxophone, vibes, bass, and drums, decorates this short film somewhat passively with the familiar and pleasant combo jazz heard at nightclubs of the time. However, in its violent sequences, the music adheres more closely to the physical action on screen. The best example of this occurs at the midpoint of the film when the camera pans away from the two men in the distance to focus instead on a gang of juvenile delinquents and their sadistic activities. As their loitering around an outdoor concert stage shifts to hurling objects at a stray kitten, the jazz subsides and is replaced by a plodding quarter-note bass line, accentuated by vibes and clarinet. An intermittent melodic progression here does not undermine the stiff constancy of the bass serving, moreover, to build the tension across an extended scene wherein the defenseless little animal is finally killed (by a very young Polanski no less). Subsequently, as the music continues, the two men are harassed and beaten. Particularly graphic is a tight shot of the second man receiving multiple blows to his bloody mouth, as the bass repeats the precomposed line. Whereas most of Komeda's soundtrack music in this student

film is familiar improvisational combo jazz, this sequence suggests that the young composer was already capable of applying jazz instrumentation idiosyncratically, that is, to reinforce the visual material as would a conventional symphonic score.

Later, when the two characters are discovered and beaten in a supply yard, this time, by a policeman wielding a two-by-four, the airy combo jazz abruptly shifts into an upbeat ride-cymbal rhythm with saxophone taking over for the clarinet as the soloing instrument. Akin to *Imitation of Life's* alleyway beating, the acceleration of tempo within the jazz idiom, as opposed to the previous example's momentary digression away from it, suffices to reinforce tension here. On its own, however, such upbeat jazz music would be embraced for its intensity, rather than any violent connotation. Here, then, is an early example, at least in the Polish context, of the modern jazz idiom's appropriation away from a live entertainment context and applied directly to graphic content for its own sake. As a result, a certain ambiguity is established between pleasure and repulsion.¹³ The next scene, for example, pursues the latter effect by allowing only the sound of the rock bashing against its victim's head

Figure 3. *Two Men and a Wardrobe* (1958). In Polanski's student film, Komeda digresses from atmospheric deployments of jazz amid the protagonists' urban odyssey in violent encounters, particularly when they encounter a gang of juvenile delinquents. Here, a plodding bass line stands out from the rest of the jazz ensemble. The composer returns to this approach in subsequent films during moments of psychological tension.

to remain after a solo vibraphone melody fades out. With the presence of jazz, the previous scene might even seem comedic, like a Keystone cop moment, if not for the juxtaposition of this disturbing violence. Whereas *Night Train* pursues a more psychological deployment of the idiom within its jazz world, Polanski's student effort applies jazz values more viscerally to violent action. Indeed, such an approach in this moment of both jazz and cinema's evolution could well have been perceived by audiences, according to the filmmaker's expressed intentions, as "quirky."

***Innocent Sorcerers* (1960)**

Anticipated by *Two Men and a Wardrobe*, the Polish manifestation of crime-jazz cinema, in general, emanated from experimental narratives focusing on disenfranchised youth within urban environments. Such content is reinforced in these films by an intermittently diegetic and extradiegetic jazz as an affirmation of both cultural disillusion and reorientation. It is more accurate to credit the respected Polish director Andrzej Wajda for initiating this urban youth narrative with his *Innocent Sorcerers* (1960). The film includes Polanski as a rowdy bass player and a rather staid Komeda as himself. Taking after Komeda's example as both a trained medical doctor and competent jazz musician, the film portrays a young sports physician and jazz drummer (Tadeusz Łomnicki) who struggles to feel a sense of purpose among his disaffected peers. Co-writing the screenplay, Jerzy Skolimowski claimed, "It's going to be a drama about the lives of young people, taking place in Warsaw, anno 1959. The main conflict in the film concerns the drama of a protagonist who is alienated, psychologically isolated from society."¹⁴

Across these three Polish films, a narrative tendency to focus on social alienation as symptomatic of the postwar milieu is evident.

In the previous examples, violent crime is configured as an inevitable consequence of this larger phenomenon. However, in this film, violence only develops briefly when an inebriated athlete at the local boxing arena assails the protagonist after disqualifying him for an untreated head wound. The ensuing fistfight is brief, but the sequence still features a graphic display of blood reemerging from the boxer's deep cut, much akin to Polanski's explicit scenes. As a decided counterculture film, *Innocent Sorcerers* takes much influence from concurrent *nouvelle vague* films like François Truffaut's *The 400 Blows* (1959) and Jean-Luc Godard's *Breathless* (1960), both of which associate jazz music with social deviance. As with Truffaut's account of juvenile delinquency, this Polish film portrays the younger generation more sympathetically as victims of social forces beyond their control. Within this moral universe, the male protagonist discovers that love of woman is the only available solace.

In the same way as *Night Train*, *Innocent Sorcerers* is a jazz-world film wherein musical presence is maintained in stage performance and nightclub scenes, as well as in scenes at the protagonist's tiny flat with his radio and tape recorder. Across these moments, Komeda offers a variety of combo jazz flavors popular at the time, invariably associating them with the younger generation performing, consuming, or discussing jazz on screen. Notable soundtrack music emerges when the protagonist discovers that the young woman (Krystyna Stypułkowska) he had lured back to his apartment has, in his momentary absence, departed. In this sequence, another plodding quarter-note bass line plays out, although, this time, with a minor blues melody on muted saxophone. Accordingly, Komeda builds a similar sense of tension as in the hooligan scene of *Two Men and a Wardrobe*.

Unlike the visceral emphasis in Polanski's student film, however, the music here takes

Figure 4. *Innocent Sorcerers* (1960). Komeda plays himself as one among an ensemble of jazz musicians in this film, although, away from their instruments, the liberated carefree lifestyle these Polish characters emulate also conjures familiar impressions of street gangs depicted in so many urban delinquency films of this period also integrating jazz music.

on a psychological dimension. As the protagonist navigates the urban sprawl, a tracking camera maintains a tight frame around his worried expression, rather than capturing the scooter's rapid movement from a distance. The ways in which this passage of film score departs from the jazz idiom, while also retaining its improvisational, melodic, and instrumental references, reinforces its psychological mode in contrast to the familiar diegetic jazz found elsewhere in the film. Just as the doleful Artie Shaw melody serves to score moments of private brooding in *Night Train*, the plodding rhythm here speaks to the trauma of the young protagonist. Ultimately, he discovers that what had seemed to be just another female conquest for him could offer something more substantial toward alleviating his social malaise.

Because this film's so-called jazzmen are portrayed as cavorting juveniles in the street, the dividing line between hooligan and "innocent sorcerer" is nevertheless tenuous at best here. Komeda's juxtaposition of diegetic nightclub jazz and a jazz-inflected score featuring repetitive upright bass lines and stark reed instrument solos reinforces this tenuousness. The young composer's attempted association between jazz and the

plight of urban youth, although mostly in diegetic contexts, would persist across additional Polish entries including Janusz Morgenstern's *See You Tomorrow* (1960), Jerzy Stefan Stawinski's *Penguin* (1965), and Jerzy Skolimowski's *Walkover* (1965) and *Barrier* (1966). It was really Polanski's first feature film effort, however, that would propel Komeda's psychological deployment of modern jazz values westward.

***Knife in the Water* (1962)**

Taking place in a recreational setting far removed from the difficult existential trappings of modern city life, Roman Polanski's *Knife in the Water* (1962) is nevertheless a psychological, crime-oriented film that addresses similar generational tensions as its urban-based contemporaries. The film—among whose screenwriters was, again, Jerzy Skolimowski—enjoyed more international acclaim and American art house currency than any other Polish production of the 1960s. This encouraged both filmmakers to abandon Poland's restrictive conditions and find more tolerant production circumstances elsewhere—bringing Komeda along with them. With only three characters, the

narrative assumes an even more pronounced allegorical mode. On the way to the Masurian Lake District outside Warsaw, an affluent middle-aged representative of the Polish establishment (Leon Niemczyk again) and his wife (Jolanta Umecka) pick up a transient (Zygmunt Malanowicz). Set aboard a sailboat appropriately named after the female character, the film, according to Haltof, portrays “a fierce rivalry” between “the worldly journalist and the insecure hitchhiker who challenges him.”¹⁵

Really, though, it is the married man who feels “insecure” in this scenario. He insists on bringing the male stranger along to prove that his aging masculinity still warrants the spousal devotion of his much younger partner. Rather than a “fierce rivalry,” what develops is an intermittently pleasant, but often uncomfortable, sailing trip for all three characters. Despite his multiple attempts to disembark, the young man is provoked into serving as an inferior deckhand, which does not escape the empathy of the similarly patronized married woman. Prior to enjoying an impromptu tryst in the husband’s absence, these two “innocent sorcerers” affirm their generation’s dearth of opportunity within postwar Polish society. Even admitting her unfaithfulness, she later informs her husband that he has not accidentally drowned their humiliated guest after all, although he rejects this report. Emulating the open endings of *The 400 Blows* and *Breathless*, the film concludes vaguely without revealing whether or not the female character makes any attempt to maintain the facts.

No crime is ever committed in this film, but akin to *Night Train*, the sailboat becomes a jazz-inflected microcosm for examining basic sociological tensions, this time, between the Polish counterculture and their parents’ generation. A moral universe of nautical mishaps encroaches on a character whose aggressive attempt to position his partner as a trophy wife among his other

possessions finally gets the better of him. Not only maintaining what Haltof describes as the film’s “vibrating, jazzy tempo and mood,” Komeda’s jazz score pursues a more intimate function in this crime-oriented narrative.¹⁶ Two alternating thematic passages, one with a gracefully descending melodic pattern, reinforce the pleasant moments shared aboard the sailboat. Removed from its typical urban association in postwar cinema, the presence of contemporary jazz in this halcyon context brings the music closer to the artistic intentions of its African American visionaries, for example, those of John Coltrane. The 1962 *Coltrane* album’s second track, “Soul Eyes” (from a jazz ballad by Mal Waldron), compiled with similar works on *The Gentle Side of John Coltrane* (1975), resembles these Komeda compositions in its sentimental mood, elaborate chord changes, and relaxed $\frac{4}{4}$ tempo, as well as its intimate quartet ensemble of saxophone, piano, bass, and drums. Of course, I have no stake in proving that Komeda or Swedish tenor saxophonist Bernt Rosengren, for that matter, was inspired by this recording specifically. Rather, I mention it in the context of Coltrane and others’ inclination to juxtapose “gentle” ballads with frenetic hard bop material at this time, as is the case on *Giant Steps* (1960) where the tranquil “Naima” appears among the rest of the influential album’s tracks. Komeda, as I shall explain, dares a similar juxtaposition in this film’s jazz score, albeit as an available means to evoke the emotional vicissitudes of the characters—rather than as an artistic gestalt per se.

Beyond establishing their melodic themes, these musical cues are too brief to allow the soloing instruments to improvise for long. In this way, they are merely fleeting references to modern jazz, as in *Two Men and a Wardrobe*. They serve nevertheless to comment on the shifting psychological condition of the characters throughout the narrative. Unlike a jazz-world context

Figure 5. *Knife in the Water* (1962). Multiple depictions of collective tranquility aboard the sailboat in this film are underscored by an atmospheric jazz akin to the so-called gentle side of Coltrane's music around this time. Such sequences are countered by moments of psychological tension between the three characters, in one case, scored by a passage of erratic soloing also citing Coltrane's post-bop work.

wherein the idiom becomes omnipresent in its spectrum of diegetic and extradiegetic origins, this strategy of intimate film scoring becomes apparent in scenes of character conflict. The first of these occurs when the two men wrangle with each other as they pull the boat through a narrow causeway from the shore. Fed up with being treated as another “baroness,” the young man only reapplies himself to the task when the woman threatens to take over. After the vessel resumes its course, a brief cue of frenetic saxophone soloing affirms the accumulating tension within their sexual triangle. Again, the reference resembles Coltrane's recordings after he parted ways with Miles Davis, but this time, Komeda's score emulates the improvisational quality of Coltrane's *Giant Steps*, the track entitled “Countdown” in particular.

On the one hand, the sailing context of Komeda's thematic compositions may readily be associated with the “gentle side” of Coltrane's expressivity. On the other hand, it would be problematic to align the visionary saxophonist's hard-bop soloing technique to a unilateral notion of trauma if one acknowledges the overtly spiritualized intentions of *A Love Supreme* (1964) or the highly erratic free jazz pursued in later projects such as

Meditations (1966), *Cosmic Music* (1968), or *Om* (1969). In other words, Komeda's film score co-opts these modern jazz values regardless of how much or how little their original artistic intention or inspiration may align with the narrative. Instead, the composer renders these glimpses of jazz music purely in terms of their generic ability to reinforce narrative content. Tranquil jazz, then, confers a character's peace of mind, while erratic jazz indicates inner angst, not unlike a conventional symphonic approach to film scoring.

Modern jazz's investment in testing musical boundaries is also exploited in the film's climactic scene just after a violent confrontation between the two male characters sends the younger one into the water. To reinforce the tension that the couple experiences as they search the sailboat's environs in vain, Komeda once again singles out the upright bass for its heavy-handed tonality. Digressing from a familiar jazz combo mode, as in his previous films, an alternating three-note pattern persists alone, although with an additional upright bass soloing over it. Unsurprisingly, such an unlikely ensemble of two bass players achieves harmonic dissonance or, rather, a *tubbiness* whenever they share the lower register. It also demonstrates the

degree to which the composer was willing to frustrate any expectation of a “jazzy mood” offered by the music appearing elsewhere. In this way, Komeda’s film music embraces both the familiarity of established nightclub jazz and the modern jazz idiom’s spirit of experimentation at the same time. In any case, this is, again, only a brief cue of soundtrack music commenting on character psychology in this moment, as in other moments. Earlier in the film, an ascending saxophone melody imitates the young man’s progression up the ship’s mast. Normally, what is historically referred to as “mickey-mousing” physical action onscreen would seem naïve, but within these open parameters of jazz reference, Komeda’s aesthetic choice here seems more whimsical, even playful.

***Repulsion* (1965)**

The Polish trajectory of cinematic crime-jazz influence was mobilized by the 1960 Resolution of the Central Committee Secretariat of the Polish United Workers’ Party, which, in any case, quashed the creative ambitions of the so-called Polish School of Soviet Thaw films in the previous decade. Haltof affirms, “The intentions behind the latter directive, which were fully implemented in the 1960s, were twofold: to neutralize the popularity of foreign ‘bourgeois’ films and to turn Polish society’s attention away from the pressing economic problems experienced under Władysław Gomułka’s regime.”¹⁷ After making *Knife in the Water*, Polanski migrated to France. Skolimowski remained in Poland to direct a handful of Komeda-scored films of his own but eventually left for Belgium to make *Le Départ* (1967), also scored by Komeda, about a young sports car enthusiast. Finding no opportunity in France, Polanski then headed to England where, based on the international recognition his first feature achieved, he was offered a chance to try his hand at a Hammer-produced horror

film. Propelled by the success of Herbert L. Strock’s *Blood of Dracula* and Terence Fisher’s *The Curse of Frankenstein*, both released in 1957, this studio’s exploitation-driven producers would eventually seek to update these gothic contexts after the Hollywood release of Hitchcock’s *Psycho* (1960).¹⁸

Unlike at home in Poland, the filmmaker was thus able to maintain his own creative interests. At least initially, in the same way as Skolimowski and his other filmmaking peers, the young director was more interested in contemporary situations. As a foreign director, he was compelled, however, to prove himself through more popular genre contexts first. According to Robert Murphy, *Repulsion* “attempts the harder task of inserting art cinema themes—alienation, disturbed sexuality, the dividing line between reality and fantasy—into a genre horror film.”¹⁹ Eschewing any metaphysical or pseudoscientific trappings, this 1965 film’s narrative accomplishes this reification of the horror genre by making its female protagonist, Carol (Catherine Deneuve), a homicidal schizophrenic in modern London. The film nevertheless conforms to a pattern of misogynistic British films targeting ethnic immigrants including Lance Comfort’s *Daughter of Darkness* (1948), Michael Powell and Emeric Pressburger’s *Gone to Earth* (1950), and Basil Dearden’s *Sapphire* (1959). In the first of these, for example, an ethnically mixed Irish woman is strangely predisposed to murder. At the same time, it should be noted that, as is the case in this much earlier film, *Repulsion*’s female protagonist is portrayed as totally irresistible to the men she encounters. This perceived ability of ethnic or otherwise foreign otherness to provoke unchecked sexual impulses in white Englishmen is coded as “Irish Gypsy” in *Daughter of Darkness* and “Belgian” in Polanski’s horror film. Although the latter narrative is less oriented around skin or even hair color, the ideological threat to “Englishness”

as well as a notion of social stability associated with it persists. In other words, such alluring women or, rather, exoticized figures from elsewhere threaten to upend the familiar everyday progress of a relatively confined society experienced through multiple generations. In such a xenophobic moral universe of storytelling, not unlike vampires and other gothic monsters, these modernized characters must eventually be eradicated.

In its decided adherence to the horror genre, *Repulsion* becomes a pivotal film in the transnational emergence of the horror jazz film score. Whereas *Daughter of Darkness* remains safely within crime-oriented drama by keeping its homicidal activity off-screen, Polanski's film emulates the example set by Hammer films toward graphic depictions of violent murder. Musical values of the modern jazz idiom, in keeping with the director's previous films, play an intimate role in this visceral agenda. Where information is otherwise scant as to more specific circumstances, Grzebałkowska's biography quotes a Polish journal's interview with Komedą as claiming, "The British trade unions wouldn't grant me permission to undertake the work. As a result, the music to *Repulsion* had been written by a well-known American composer staying in England—Chico Hamilton."²⁰ Revealing in this brief account is the fact that many African American jazz musicians in the postwar era not only found work overseas but, in a few cases, managed to prove themselves capable as film composers for eventual work in Hollywood. Only in the previous year, for example, Quincy Jones had exploited modern jazz values in his score for *The Pawnbroker* to reinforce male protagonist impaling his hand down a spindle in the film's climax of Holocaust-driven psychological trauma.

In any case, toward affirming Polanski's close attention to film scoring, Mazierska's study of his work opines, "What strikes me is how similar the music in *Repulsion*

seems in its sound, atmosphere and function within the narrative to that composed by Komedą."²¹ This evaluation is both true and not true. Early in the film, two sequences employ a familiar upbeat combo jazz sound, one of which is included as "Carol's Walk" on drummer Hamilton's *Chic* Chic Chico* album of the same year. As Carol saunters along London sidewalks, the walking bass supports a soloing flute accompanied by the electric guitar of Hungarian musician Gabor Szabo, who also orchestrated the film's music. In the second such sequence, these three instruments solo together over a similar $\frac{4}{4}$ rhythm, demonstrating what some have termed "chamber jazz," an impulse shared by both Hamilton and Komedą to make the small ensemble more classically integrated beyond the standard distinction between soloists and rhythm section. But these deployments of atmospheric jazz, as in the urban traversal sequences of *Two Men and a Wardrobe* or the sailing sequences in *Knife in the Water*, are relatively light and unobtrusive.

At the same time, working within the modern jazz idiom's rigorous spirit of experimentation, Hamilton, like Komedą, was willing to explore a cinematic psychological reference in what could still be recognizable as jazz-inflected composition. Later in the film, after her suitor (John Fraser) attempts a first kiss, Carol flees his car abruptly. As she rushes inside to wash her mouth out, a series of rapid-fire snare and guitar triplets ensues with a walking bass and overlying saxophone melody. This traumatic soundtrack reappears when she wanders aimlessly down a sidewalk and then once more when she slashes her assailing landlord (Patrick Wymark) to death with a hand razor. Making these pseudo-jazz cues a motif in this way emphasizes an accumulation of inner ruptures necessary for this otherwise frail character to wax homicidal.

Unlike Komedą's other jazz scores, however, Hamilton pushes the idiom and its small ensemble one step further by offering

Figure 6. *Repulsion* (1965). Replacing Komeda for this British Hammer production, Chico Hamilton's tight combo accomplishes this horror jazz sequence with frenzied snare rolls, cymbal crashes, and other abrasive effects while retaining modern jazz trappings during the female protagonist's worsening traumas. Here, the film's ambivalence toward this androphobic character and her homicidal tendencies is pronounced in the apparent sexual gratification she experiences.

horror stingers in moments where shock is intended. This also occurs at multiple points in the film, such as when the drifting Carol injures a client's finger during a manicure, or when she first hallucinates a male predator's ambush in her bedroom. Outside of this film's larger jazz-score context, a cymbal crash combined with bursts of shrill flute in these moments would scarcely reference the idiom, despite Hamilton keeping within the limits of his small ensemble. In other moments, such musical effects occur within a jazz-oriented composition. In two cases when Carol is alone in the apartment, the combo jazz ensemble provides an eerie sonic corollary for the protagonist's worsening delusions by way of a dissonant electric guitar arpeggio, flute, and murmuring vibraphone, interrupted by a fusillade of abrupt cymbal crashes as multiple hands burst out from the hallway walls to envelop her.

***Rosemary's Baby* (1968)**

Such a fully realized application of modern jazz values to a horror agenda would set a precedent for Komeda's breadth of musical expression. Despite any continuity of crime-jazz association in *Cul-de-Sac* (1966) or visceral genre trappings of *The Fearless Vampire*

Killers (1967), Polanski's reinstated collaboration with his Polish friend across these subsequent British productions would not find its own horror-jazz fruition until they had left England to work on *Rosemary's Baby* (1968). Seeking to adapt Ira Levin's novel of the same name, William Castle, as with Hammer Studio's producers in Britain, came from a legacy of exploitative horror films such as *House on Haunted Hill* (1959), *The Tingler* (1959), and *The Night Walker* (1964). Having secured rights to the novel, Paramount Pictures executive Robert Evans then offered the project to Polanski. It was Polanski himself, according to Christopher Sandford's biography, who pushed for the chance to direct this film in lieu of *Downhill Racer*, a skiing drama starring Robert Redford, which was released subsequently in 1969.²²

I would suggest, then, that the arrival of Polish crime-jazz influence to Hollywood in this way was facilitated by both the momentum of Polanski's art-house reputation and his own artistic attraction to narratives of externalized psychological trauma—finding their apex in *The Tenant* (1976). With the director himself in the role of a delusional male protagonist, this bleak, nightmarish film was produced in France in the aftermath

of unfortunate events that included Kameda's death, the brutal murder of Polanski's American wife Sharon Tate, and the statutory rape scandal that would compel him to quit the US permanently. Although Mazierska affirms that French composer Phillipe Sarde's music "accompanies the main character" as in *Repulsion*, saying, "Its melancholia reflects the dark and sorrowful ambience of the flat that gradually overwhelms the tenant,"²³ modern jazz values are no longer assigned to this re-emergent narrative context.

Appearing at the culturally cathartic close of the decade, *Rosemary's Baby* can be understood as a confluence of the Satanic strain of female paranoid narratives dating as far back as Mark Robson's *The Seventh Victim* (1943) and as recent as J. Lee Thompson's *Eye of the Devil* (1966)—and the concurrent pattern of demonized jazz. The older Hollywood film follows a young woman (Kim Hunter) tracking down her missing sister (Jean Brooks) in New York City and finding herself embroiled in designs of a murderous Satanic cult in the process. The latter British production portrays an affluent English woman (Deborah Kerr) joining her husband (David Niven) at an old family chateau in northern France where she eventually discovers his role in an agrarian community's longstanding ritual of human sacrifice. In her first feature film part, Sharon Tate plays an alluring pagan enchantress, and considering she first met Polanski in London after filming was completed, it is plausible that the director became familiar with this film, especially according to her casting in *The Fearless Vampire Killers* the following year.

Beyond the gothic trappings of New York's Dakota apartment building used as the primary location for the nefarious secret society encroaching on the female protagonist (Mia Farrow) and her complicit husband (John Cassavetes), or even occult references dating further back to Edgar G. Ulmer's *The Black Cat* (1934), it is the basic appeal of

the paranoid narrative to countercultural viewers that connects a film like *Repulsion* to *Rosemary's Baby*. These narratives do not characterize paranoia as a form of neurosis as much as they provide justifiable grounds for it. Although the final shot of Polanski's British film reveals Carol to be a disturbed, wide-eyed child in an old family photograph, her delusions of rape prepare her rather appropriately for her middle-aged landlord's assault. In a comparatively intellectual, ratiocinative mindset, Rosemary pieces together clues revealing the elderly neighbors' designs upon her, although at a point too late to thwart them. Because sensations of fear are always validated in such a moral universe, the visceral aspect of the horror genre only made these paranoid narratives more therapeutic for viewers in the cultural moment of the film's release. The implication that these female protagonists are trapped within a long-established social system resonated not only with a feminist sensibility, but also with young American audiences more broadly. A growing distrust of their parents' generation and the society they represented would find the validation that such films promised across the subsequent decade.

By this time, Kameda's robust experience as a film composer encouraged him to push beyond the limitations of a combo jazz ensemble and pursue a more orchestrated, choral approach, as is evident in both *Barrier* and *The Fearless Vampire Killers*. In this way, he was becoming closer to a classically trained Italian film composer such as Ennio Morricone, who effortlessly hybridized symphonic scoring and elements of popular music, for example, by having a jazz drummer reinforce a full orchestra with a vocal chorus, as in *Maddalena* (1971), a coproduction also directed by Polish filmmaker Jerzy Kawalerowicz. As far back as 1961, Kameda claimed, "Jazz harmonizes well with the atmosphere of films with contemporary subject matter; especially psychological

and detective films, and thrillers.” Yet, in the same Polish interview, he stated, “I go beyond jazz in film. That departure is going to be something new in my work as a composer.”²⁴

The vocal approach he applies to these previous films can also be found in *Rosemary's Baby* as the opening theme, sung by Mia Farrow herself. Far from the operatic displays achieved by Edda Dell’Orso on so many Italian soundtracks around this time, the delicate timbre of her performance perfectly matches her character’s vulnerability in the film. At the same time, Komeda would not abandon jazz altogether, if for no other reason than the reappearance of an “innocent sorcerer” character who consumes the music herself. Comparing this film’s protagonist to Teresa (Françoise Dorléac) in Polanski’s *Cul-de-Sac*, Mazierska affirms Rosemary also collects jazz records. “However, in her case it signifies not her rebelliousness, but rather her desire to find peace (which is paradoxical, taking into account that jazz was often considered the soundtrack to urban pollution) and, perhaps, her ambition to become a true New Yorker.”²⁵ Regardless of what this scholar means by “urban pollution” here, it is productive to apply her basic notion of paradox to how the given musical idiom of jazz can reflect pleasure *and* trauma in a narrative context at the same time. As in *Cul-de-Sac*, Komeda pursues this contextual dichotomy in *Rosemary's Baby*.

To a certain extent, this could be considered another jazz-world film wherein diegetic manifestations of popular music are integrated with extradiegetic hints of jazz striving, moreover, to score dramatic psychological moments. The greater New York City environment of this film, as it steadily engulfs this character both inside and outside her apartment, recalls Polish disenfranchised youth entries such as *Barrier* with its urban rat-race sequences, and, at the same time, *Repulsion* with Carol’s busy London

sidewalk meanderings. But unlike *Cul-de-Sac*, for example, wherein Komeda’s thematic combo jazz alternates with Teresa spinning variations of the same material on her phonograph, *Rosemary's Baby* features many scattered cues of film score not necessarily jazz-oriented. It is accurate to note that the composer employs a conventional theme-and-variations approach of applying the main title’s vocal melody as an instrumental version elsewhere, or, more specifically, as Mazierska affirms, to “activities associated with the arrival of a new baby.”²⁶ While this is essentially true, it is more precise to say Komeda’s “Lullaby” theme is intimately associated with Rosemary’s consciousness and how it transforms across the film from a state of passive faith in her existence to one of informed disillusion. Within the moral universe of this film, in other words, the protagonist’s Catholic assumptions that people in a modern urbanized society are just as sincere and good-intentioned becomes punishable, and she is ultimately consigned to nurture her Satanic offspring.

Appealing to values of the modern jazz idiom, the Polish composer reinforces this psychological transformation through the introduction of dissonant elements. After pregnant Rosemary’s chronic pain abruptly subsides amid tensions with her husband, at which point she also experiences the fetus’s first movement, the next scene has the couple cheerfully setting up a new bassinet and making other preparations. Strings faithfully play the delicate “Lullaby” melody as in the moment when the protagonist first learns she is pregnant, except that the former connotation of a nursery evoked by celesta chimes is here perverted by dissonant pitches on the instrument, now behaving like the intrusive harpsichord notes in the film’s opening theme. Such a musical strategy hints that Rosemary’s renewed optimism is fleeting according to the baby she is carrying, however healthy it would appear to be.

Extradiegetic jazz eventually works its way into this thematic accumulation toward abrasiveness at a point in the film when everyone would seem to have nefarious designs on Rosemary and her child. When she quits her apartment to seek haven from her original obstetrician, she is just as soon recaptured by her husband and the also complicit Dr. Sapirstein (Ralph Bellamy). In this sequence, as they approach the Dakota building, dissonance is again introduced into the recurrent “Lullaby” theme, this time by way of playing the melody on an electronic keyboard (or synthesizer) whose ring-modulator mode achieves a warbly effect. Audible snare brushes and repeated root notes on an upright bass establish the impression of an intimate jazz ensemble here. Once inside the lobby, Rosemary drops her purse, diverting the others’ attention just long enough for her to break away and escape into the elevator. To augment this moment’s tension, the rhythm section pauses briefly to allow a string melody to sound out over an incongruent flute ostinato. But just as the elevator doors clap shut, the snare and bass explode into a driving $\frac{6}{8}$ rhythm to support a frenzied solo trumpet wailing an ascendant atonal pattern toward an implied climax of emotional trauma for the protagonist. This dedicated passage of horror jazz only subsides after Rosemary stumbles out of the elevator, rushes down the hall, and slams the apartment door on her pursuers. But, alas, her moment of triumph is all too fleeting.

The horror-jazz association between the female protagonist’s onscreen psychological trauma and Komeda’s evocation of the modern jazz idiom here also brings the cycle of crime-jazz influence full circle—in its racist orientation toward African Americans. When the young white couple first arrives at the Dakota building to see the newly vacant apartment, the onsite manager (Elisha Cook Jr.) conducts them inside where a Black

elevator operator (D’Urville Martin) awaits. With an artificial air of condescension, the manager casually admonishes his uniformed underling for not lubricating the squeaky retractable gate. Otherwise, such a minor character, akin to the Black cabdriver later in the film, would seem insignificant. The elevator man reappears, however, in Rosemary’s half-conscious nightmare of Satanic fornication, wherein wearing a sailor uniform, he fulfills another subservient role as the helmsman of a yacht. When she approaches him on deck from behind, he simply sneers at her, “You’d be better go down below, miss.” However brief, his less-than-cordial presence here is ascribable to the ensuing scene after she descends through a portal to find herself in a gothic bedchamber where, surrounded by undressed members of the coven, Satan himself eventually mounts and inseminates her. In other words, even this marginal African American character, only exceptional for his skin color, is perceived by Rosemary to be complicit in her victimization.

Droning chords and overlapping choral melodies mostly dominate Rosemary’s Satanic rape sequence, although a soloing upright bass appears initially as a slight token of horror jazz. Such a choice nevertheless echoes Komeda’s use of this instrument in violent scenes of earlier Polish productions. Later in the film, when the others convey the protagonist back home, the African American character, restored as the apartment building’s elevator man, greets her politely according to his function. But merely by assisting the other two in gathering up items spilt from her purse and then shouting after her when she dashes into the elevator, he again appears complicit in the diabolical plot. In other words, his professional affiliation with the nefarious Dakota building already implicates him in its conspiratorial micro-society. Like the harmless cabdriver she encounters amid her attempted escape, his Blackness, along with the modern jazz

Figure 7. *Rosemary's Baby* (1968). During the female protagonist's Satanic fornication sequence, classical Hollywood's stereotypically subservient characterization for an African American is exaggerated as the demonized helmsman aboard a yacht wherein the coven awaits her below deck. Kameda's brief deployment of a soloing upright bass here offers another ironic glimpse of horror jazz.

idiom's more experimental directions away from the soothing cocktail jazz she listens to in her apartment, are configured together here as abominations of urbanized existence. This implied cultural dichotomy within parameters of the larger jazz idiom harkens back to *The Cry of Jazz* wherein a similar contrast is drawn between a complacent "white jazz" and a progressive "Black jazz." In the Satanic context of the later Hollywood production, it is the emergent derivatives of bebop across the 1960s that are demonized by association—even if Kameda sought merely to score the film according to at least partially to the relative freedom of an idiom within which he developed as a musician and composer.

Final Remarks

The larger impulse to employ musical values of the modern jazz idiom to score psychological trauma and/or visceral horror waned according to the primacy of rock music and popular hybrid forms such as progressive rock, fusion, soul, and funk, however limited their potential proved to be as film music. African American jazz musicians seeking soundtrack work, such as Herbie Hancock, J. J. Johnson, and Grant Green, catered to the soul and funk demands of 1970s Blaxploitation films. By the time Skolimowski

arrived in England to seek better filmmaking opportunities like Polanski before him, not only had Kameda perished, but popular culture had shifted its attention away from jazz. Bookending the subsequent decade, his British productions *Deep End* (1970), another male coming-of-age entry, and *The Shout* (1978), a psychological horror narrative resembling both *Knife in the Water* and *Cul-de-Sac* with its triangulated characters, featured film music by progressive rock musicians (Can and Genesis) in lieu of any jazz. Between these overseas releases and at the peak of his abilities, Polanski directed *Chinatown* (1974), a period crime film steeped in nostalgia for the classical Hollywood era. Anticipating big-budget neo-noir remakes such as *The Big Sleep* (1978), *The Postman Always Rings Twice* (1981), and *D.O.A.* (1988), this highly acclaimed film might have celebrated prewar jazz in this context. Instead, for the film's main theme, Jerry Goldsmith's score merely allows a solo trumpet to sound out a mournful melody over a conventional string section.

While there *was* a steady trajectory of crime-jazz soundtracks persisting into the 1970s in other Hollywood films such as Norman Jewison's *The Thomas Crown Affair* (1968), William Friedkin's *The French Connection* (1971), and Michael Winner's *Death*

Wish (1974), I would also point to the psychological strain of crime-jazz cinema more attributable to overseas influence, as found in rarer cases such as *The Conversation* or *Taxi Driver*. Perhaps the closest intimacy between modern jazz in its then-state of avant-garde evolution and visceral crime-horror contexts is to be found in Italian *giallo* films, namely Dario Argento's *Cat o' Nine Tails* (1971), Lucio Fulci's *Woman in a Lizard's Skin* (1971), and Mario Caiano's *Eye in the Labyrinth* (1972), where musical reference to both Miles Davis's albums *In a Silent Way* (1969) and *Bitches Brew* (1970) is evident. Such horror-jazz cues could well have been encouraged not only by what Quincy Jones accomplished for *The Pawnbroker* and *In Cold Blood*, but also by what Chico Hamilton accomplished for *Repulsion*—and finally what Komeda had just accomplished for *Rosemary's Baby*.

To better appreciate, in any case, how these African American jazz composers would appear to have contributed to the media-manufacture of otherness, even in an ethnic context, compels some review of the narrative and stylistic patterns within the Polish trajectory of crime-jazz cinema. Rather than perceiving a clearcut aesthetic agenda, it may be more productive to understand the greater filmmaking impetus here as multiple impulses coordinating toward a polyvalent, even conflicting array of possible meanings. According to such a phenomenon, consumers may respond to a range of available gratifications—variably therapeutic depending on an individual viewer's cultural experience. Especially across *Night Train*, *Knife in the Water*, and *Rosemary's Baby*, one may notice a similar assemblage of characters within a confined location through which larger symptomatic behaviors are revealed. In the case of these three films taken together, a notion of paranoia emerges as a characteristically modern trauma, and yet, increasingly, such a mindset becomes justifiable in

context. In the first film, characters aboard the train learn their collective fear of criminality is misdirected. In the subsequent film, the would-be sailboat captain almost sees his presumptions of adultery gratified. Finally, Rosemary ends up confirming every suspicion she has about others in her apartment building.

If we include *Repulsion* within this evolution of paranoid narratives, another microcosm reveals itself in the walkable portion of London between Carol's apartment and the beauty clinic where she works. Her paranoid delusions not only anticipate the landlord's attempted rape but also the young suitor's forced entry at an earlier point, which could have led to similar behavior had she not struck him down. At the same time, the moral universe of these films also finds their protagonists punishable according to their traumas. None of them emerge from their struggles with any sense of victory. Within these conditions of storytelling, a film may readily evoke a prejudicial stance toward characters positioned as antagonists, such as Rosemary's much older neighbors and the urban Black elevator man. Alternatively, a film may elicit degrees of xenophobia even toward protagonists who threaten both a community's homogeneity and homeostasis, as is the case with Carol or the multiethnic character in *Daughter of Darkness*. If these biases are cultivated at the same time, as in *Repulsion* according to its pairing of a schizophrenic foreigner with so many unrestrained male libidos, a greater sense of ambiguity may arise. Is Carol to be deemed an innocent victim, then, or does the film configure her as responsible for her irresistibility in this context?

A pronounced dichotomy between film-score evocations of a safe, palatable jazz and a challenging, avant-garde jazz also developed across the work of these Polish collaborators, especially *Knife in the Water*, *Repulsion*, and *Rosemary's Baby*. In the first two cases, this

contrast is clarified through atmospheric and psychological modes of extradiegetic music. In fleeting moments of *Knife in the Water* when the boat is sailing on the lake, a notion of harmony between the characters is implied, reinforced by Komeda's soothing saxophone melody. But after the two men grapple with each other along the bank, its erratic soloing lacks a visual corollary. In *Repulsion*, Carol's sidewalk progressions, at least initially, seem untroubled according to Chico Hamilton's pleasant combo jazz. Later, however, a decided horror-jazz music bursts in whenever appropriate to the character's abrupt emotional turns. Instead of relying purely on film score to clarify the female protagonist's mindset, *Rosemary's Baby* accomplishes something closer to a jazz world by juxtaposing the "white jazz" heard on Rosemary's phonograph with the erratic and dissonant "Black jazz" during her experiences of inner crisis. Throughout this evolution of crime-jazz filmmaking, evocations of progressive jazz are associated with psychological trauma. If Polanski and Komeda's path from Poland to Hollywood reflects a popular embrace of European arthouse influence, at least at the point of *Rosemary's Baby*, then a certain "cry of jazz" echoed in the process, albeit ironically.

My larger project is to trace the cultural impact of two major strains of American popular media, namely jazz and the urban crime drama, in terms of their confluence beyond postwar Hollywood. Because the musical idiom's roots and pivotal developments are attributable to African American artistry, degrees of implied social deviance persisted in these overseas cinemas even where no Black presence is visible. This is why the historical marriage of jazz to crime-based narratives is a transnational phenomenon, or at least in cultural contexts where racial identity has been partially defined against perception of African Blackness or

ethnic negritude as such. In the postwar era, the pervasive diffusion of American popular music alongside distribution of Hollywood product mobilized these diasporas of crime-jazz filmmaking in many national contexts, which, in some cases, impacted American musicians and filmmakers in turn. The Polish crime-jazz association is unique for mobilizing a palpable countercurrent of crime-jazz filmmaking from Poland to Hollywood, whose collaborations included African American musicians along the way. Racist depiction of a Black character appeared only in the Stateside production at the end of this trajectory. Nevertheless, the perception of social deviance as criminality, ethnic otherness, or both implied as the same thing is persistently mediated by musical values of the modern jazz idiom—even when African American composers were involved. The explanation for such irony lies in the sheer momentum and complexity of mainstream cultural influence on a global scale. In other words, for a time at least, opportunity knocked.

NOTES

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2. Pietraszewski, *Jazz in Poland*, 44–45.
3. Pietraszewski, *Jazz in Poland*, 48.
4. Pietraszewski, *Jazz in Poland*, 54.
5. Magdalena Grzebałkowska, *Komeda: A Private Life in Jazz* (Equinox, 2020), 33.
6. Grzebałkowska, *Komeda*, 36.
7. Jon Panish, *The Color of Jazz Race and Representation in Postwar American Culture* (University Press of Mississippi, 1997), 97.
8. David Butler, *Jazz Noir: Listening to Music from Phantom Lady to The Last Seduction* (Praeger, 2002); Jans B. Wager, *Jazz and Cocktails: Rethinking Race and the Sound of Film Noir* (University of Texas Press, 2017).
9. Marek Haltof, *Polish Cinema: A History* (Berghahn, 2018), 116.
10. Haltof, *Polish Cinema*, 117.

11. Haltof, *Polish Cinema*, 154.
12. Grzebałkowska, *Komeda*, 149.
13. Julian Hanich, *Cinematic Emotion in Horror Films and Thrillers: The Aesthetic Paradox of Pleasurable Fear* (Routledge, 2011), 100.
14. Grzebałkowska, *Komeda*, 203.
15. Haltof, *Polish Cinema*, 157.
16. Haltof, *Polish Cinema*, 157.
17. Haltof, *Polish Cinema*, 159.
18. Robert Murphy, "Polanski and Skolimowski in Swinging London," in *Polish Cinema in a Transnational Context*, ed. Ewa Mazierska and Michael Goddard (University of Rochester Press, 2014), 262.
19. Murphy, "Polanski and Skolimowski," 262.
20. Grzebałkowska, *Komeda*, 316.
21. Ewa Mazierska, *Roman Polanski: The Cinema of a Cultural Traveller* (Bloomsbury, 2007), 103.
22. Christopher Sandford, *Polanski: A Biography* (Macmillan, 2009), 110.
23. Mazierska, *Roman Polanski*, 105.
24. Grzebałkowska, *Komeda*, 204.
25. Mazierska, *Roman Polanski*, 104.
26. Mazierska, *Roman Polanski*, 104.